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Executive Summary

This Knowledge and Information Sharing – Phase 1 report describes the activities implemented and resources developed in the first three years of the HEAP project, in order to support data providers within the consortium to effectively upload data to the informatics platform.

The aim when organising events and developing resources for data providers within the HEAP consortium is to create synergies between education, dissemination and communication activities. This enables the target audiences to simultaneously learn, be informed, and generate lasting and widely accessible educational and dissemination material. The collaborative work undertaken at the HEAP Bring Your Own Data workshops, which then leads to co-creation of learning resources such as the FAIR video series, “Swamped?”, is an example of this approach. This approach also underpins the development of the HEAP software platform and secure IT infrastructure.

The learner profiles for uploading data to HEAP during Phase 1 (2020-2022) consist of epidemiologists, biologists and medical researchers, biobank managers and applied AI users from HEAP work packages (WPs) 3,4,5, 8 and 9, representing the HEAP pilot projects.

The key topics for learning resources and events concern the following: ethics and law; FAIR data principles and data interoperability; the informatics platform and knowledge engine (PaaS or Platform as a Service); and the secure infrastructure (IaaS or Infrastructure as a Service). The lead WPs for these topics are WP2,7, 6 and 10.

Learning and informational resources developed during Phase 1 include a video summarising on the key features of the Hopsworks platform, a FAIR data self-assessment service supported by a series of short videos introducing FAIR data principles, and a range of on-line tutorials and resources on how to use the Hopsworks informatics platform and access the secure infrastructure.

Alongside these resources, the HEAP WPs produced scientific publications and related deliverables containing a wealth of information to inform the development of learning resources for users of the HEAP platform in Phase 2 (2023-2024) of the HEAP project.

The learning and informational events held during Phase 1 include a series of practical Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops, jointly organised by WPs 7, 11 and 1, giving the data providers a forum in which to define requirements for the informatics platform and to test the features. More structured events included presentations of new features of Hopsworks, the FAIR data and ELSI developments.

The lead partner for WP 11 is the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), in collaboration with all partners of the HEAP consortium.

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1 Introduction

This Knowledge and Information Sharing – Phase 1 report describes the activities implemented and resources developed in the first three years of the HEAP project, in order to support **data providers within the consortium** to effectively upload data to the informatics platform.

Although some of the dissemination materials produced during Phase 1 are suitable for a wide audience, this report does not specifically cover wider dissemination to the other HEAP target audience groups.

Education and dissemination - approach

The aim when organising events and developing resources for data providers within the HEAP consortium is to create synergies between education, dissemination and communication activities. This enables the target audiences to simultaneously learn, be informed, and generate lasting and widely accessible educational and dissemination material. The work undertaken by the WP 11 team is highly collaborative, and always involves one or several other HEAP partners, as seen at the HEAP 'Bring Your Own Data' workshops, and also in resource development, such as the FAIR video series, "Swamped?". As well as being a joint project with WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing, the "Swamped?" series received contributions from WP2 Ethics and Regulations, WP3 Large sample cohorts, and WP8 Epigenetics.

This collaborative approach also underpins the development of technical learning materials on the HEAP software platform and secure IT infrastructure. The HEAP project team develop and test technical solutions using real data from ongoing research projects, with results, such as bioinformatics pipelines, then shared and reused by the other HEAP pilot projects (Phase 1), before being more widely promoted and disseminated (Phase 2)

The learner profiles for uploading data to HEAP during Phase 1 (2020-2022) consist of epidemiologists, biologists and medical researchers, biobank managers and applied AI users from HEAP WPs 3,4,5, 8 and 9, representing the HEAP pilot projects:

- Cervical Cancer Screening Cohort (Karolinska Institute. WP3)
- Finnish Maternity Cohort (University of Oulu. WP3)
- HPV Vaccination Cohort (Tampere University Hospital. WP3)
- Consumer cohort (Statens Serum Institute. WP4)
- Wearable Data Collection Study (Karolinska Institute. WP5)
- Lifestyle cohort (University of Innsbruck. WP8)
- Machine Learning for metagenomics (ICM, University of Warsaw WP9)

The key topics for learning resources and events concern ethics and law (WP2), FAIR data principles and data interoperability (WP7), the informatics

platform and knowledge engine (PaaS or Platform as a Service) (WP6), and the secure infrastructure (IaaS or Infrastructure as a Service) (WP10).

Bring Your Own Data Workshops

The first Bring Your Own Data (BYOD#1) workshop, held in December 2020, focused on establishing a basic metadata structure for the HEAP informatics platform, and on FAIR data principles, including the HEAP Data Management Plan (Deliverable 7.1) and the Self-Assessment Service. The workshop developed a framework for production of learning resources by detailed target audience mapping (through developing “personas”) and a learning needs assessment

The second BYOD workshop (BYOD#2), held in October 2021, focused on more detailed metadata structures for different types of data, and on introducing the researchers to the technical and security features of the informatics platform. There was also a “storytelling” stream, where researchers began the co-creation of the FAIR data video tutorial series, which was later named “Swamped?”.

The technical stream of the third BYOD workshop (BYOD#3), held in November 2022, focused on testing analysis pipelines within Hopsworks, while the resources stream paved the way for Phase 2 (involving researchers from outside HEAP) by focusing on creating “use case” videos featuring the HPV meta” pipeline, and synthetic data from HPV vaccination cohort, to demonstrate the platform to a wider research community.

BYOD#3 also opened two sessions to researchers from the HEAP institutions to enable them to find out about the features of the Hopsworks informatics platform and the FAIR data toolbox developed by the WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing team.

Further resources and publications

In January 2022, following collaboration between WP6 and WP11, a [“Key features” video](#) was released on the HEAP YouTube channel, showcasing the main features of the Hopsworks platform for data providers. The Hopsworks website also features a [wide range of tutorials and documentation](#) about the informatics platform that is the basis for HEAP.

The project members began to publish in scientific journals, with key publications captured on the [Resources](#) page of the HEAP website. Notable publications that appeared in 2022 that will inform future training materials and events include [“The 10 commandments of Ethical Medical AI”](#) and [“Using HPV meta for Human Papillomavirus RNA quality detection”](#).

The HEAP project also shared the tools it is developing, including the FAIR data toolbox, FAIR data Self-Assessment Service, and the [HEAP project GitHub repository](#) to the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) on-line [toolbox](#).

The bigger picture

This Knowledge and Information Sharing – Phase 1 report (Deliverable 11.3) builds on Deliverable 11.2 - Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan, that sets out the overall approach and activities to maximise the impact of HEAP through Education, dissemination and training and activities for the target audience groups, and exploitation of the project results.

This Phase 1 work lays the foundations for the final two years of the project, where the objective is to produce and disseminate learning and communications material to encourage and support **European scientists beyond the consortium** to use HEAP for research. This will help to secure a legacy for HEAP as a scientific resource and will be the subject of Deliverable 11.4 Knowledge and Information Sharing, Phase 2.

2 Target audience

This deliverable 11.3 focuses on data providers within the HEAP Consortia. As the first step in designing appropriate Knowledge and Information sharing activities, the WP11 team began detailed target audience mapping in Year 1 of the project, focusing on Epidemiologists, Biologists/medical researchers, biobank managers and applied AI users.

Target audience group	Specific target audiences
Research	Data providers, Epidemiologists, Biologist/Medical researchers, Bioinformatics, Biobank managers, ICT scientists, Ethical experts, Applied AI users

Source: HEAP project proposal

HEAP personas

As described in Deliverable 11.2, the WP11 team used a “Persona interview” approach to target representatives of the “Research” group, in particular the researchers from the HEAP pilot projects and involved in developing the HEAP platform, during the first HEAP “Bring Your Own Data” workshop in 2020.

Persona details/HEAP Work Package	Interaction with HEAP (data provider/data processor/system designer) and brief summary of learning needs
Epidemiologist, biologist, medical researcher, biobank manager Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5, 8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Bioinformatician WP 8 and 9 (Epigenomics, Microbiomics).	Data processor. Curates data, upstream processing.
Applied AI users Potentially all platform users. WPs 3,4,5, 8,9	Data processor. Refines algorithms/weighting for downstream data processing.

The relevant Persona interview results are presented in Annex 1.

In Year 3 of the project, the WP11 team summarised the Persona approach in a scientific publication submitted to Open Research Europe (under review - publication expected in early 2023).

Learning Needs Assessment

The WP11 team conducted a Learning Needs Assessment (see Annex 2) with the HEAP partners to identify training needs by listing the prerequisite knowledge and skills needed to be a competent user of the HEAP platform, and any related training requirements.

One of the main benefits of the Learning Needs Assessment approach is to highlight the expertise within the HEAP consortia to develop learning materials, as shown in the table below.

HEAP partner/WP	Key topic specialism
MLC, WP 2 Ethics and Regulations	Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues
MUG, WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing	Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles
Logical Clocks, WP6 – Informatic platform and Knowledge Engine	HEAP Data Management and analysis services
CSC, WP10 – Secure infrastructure for Big Data	HEAP Data Management and analysis services (HEAP data processor)
University of Innsbruck, WP8, Epigenomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)
University of Warsaw, WP9, Microbiomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)

For each group listed above, the Learning Needs Assessment identifies the skills and knowledge required to become a competent user of the HEAP platform and predicts learning needs. It also provides information required to structure training materials.

Pilot projects – description of data

The target audience for Phase 1 consists of data providers within the HEAP consortia associated with the six data cohorts as summarised in the table below.

Cohort	HEAP project objectives	Data type/format	Data origin	Data size
Lifestyle cohort (UI) 156 participants	To evaluate how intermittent fasting and smoking cessation impacts on DNA methylation markers of disease and ageing, and other biomarkers of health and disease (clinical, microbiome, metabolome, molecular, cellular endpoints)	-Consent Information -Participation data (e.g. randomisation data, etc.) (Encrypted CSV) -Methylation data -Sequence data (microbiome) -Metabolome data -Reports (Word/PDF/HTML)	Biological samples and lifestyle data from participants	TB scale (<500 TB) Longitudinal collection of at least 3 biological samples from >100 women for up to 6 timepoints -Methylation and sequencing data, other molecular or metabolic data (tabular)
Cervical screening cohort (KI) Samples from healthy tissue, pre-neoplastic lesions and cancer from the Swedish national cervical screening program	To evaluate internal exposome (virus, bacteria) via cervical exfoliated cells. The sequencing analysis of specimens together with metadata aims to identify and characterize risk factors for disease.	-Consent Information -Register data (SAS, MySQL) -Sample data (LIMS, CSV format) -Exposome data (sequencing data following standards as in TCGA database)	-Samples from screening program -National Cervical Screening Register data -National health registers at National Board of Health and Welfare	TB scale (>500 Tb). >800 000 samples from 450 000 unique women. -140 000 new women are enrolled annually. Although we cannot sequence every specimen, data on every patient will be listed.

Cohort	HEAP project objectives	Data type/format	Data origin	Data size
Finnish Maternity cohort (UOULU) Population base biobank	To understand the exposome over time and over generations using data from a population base biobank.	Baseline data for 1.000.000 healthy participants: -Consent Information -Participation data (Encrypted CSV) -Reports (Word/PDF/HTML)	-Finnish National prenatal screening of pregnant women -FMC screening results (HIV, syphilis, hepatitis B, rubella)	Subset 10 * 2.000.000 samples from 1M participants for microbiome data. Baseline data: GB scale (in the future) Sequence data: TB scale
HPV vaccination cohort (KI)	To establish a randomised stratified intervention cohort related to the impact of exposure to health interventions over time.	Baseline data for 60,000 healthy participants: -Consent information -Participation data (Encrypted CSV) -Documentation (Word/PDF/HTML) -Participant data: HPV centre DB -Sample data: HPV centre LIMS -Sequencing data: HPV centre data storage (server and cluster)	-Intervention trial follow-up. In addition -STD follow-up results (HPV and chlamydia)	Subset 40 HPV types 60.000 participants * (5 to 10) for microbiome data. Baseline data: Gigabyte scale Sequence data: TB scale
Consumer cohort (SSI) To use consumer purchase data to continuously model and assess the household consumed exposome's impact on health. -Main study – ad on Storebox website (400 participants as of end 2022). -After COVID study -IBD study (around 20 participants) -Better health generations (potential additional study)	To identify consumer purchases that may impact health, in particular inflammatory bowel disease. -Enrichment pipeline (of consumer data) is being developed	-Consumer purchase data: JSON (received format) saved in MS SQL DB This will be enriched by data from: - Purchase items information (classification, nutritional) -Clinical data from registers -Other research projects SQL DB, CSV -Scientific reports Word/PDF/HTML	-Commercial digital receipt providers (Storebox) -Danish (national health) registers -Clinical quality databases (clinical information) - Loyalty programmes (potential for the future)	Depends on the number of participants. Average enrolment information from 4-5 years. Raw consumer purchase data: GB scale Enriched data: GB scale

Cohort	HEAP project objectives	Data type/format	Data origin	Data size
<p>Wearable data collection study (OULU) Pilot study on 100 pregnant volunteers from Finnish maternity cohort to investigate how the exposome influences maternal and infant health. Timescale of study (2 winter months, 2 summer months). Participant provide biological samples every month (5 samples in total. One baseline, one for each month of the study). Roughly between month 4-9 of pregnancy.</p>	<p>To produce continuous personal exposome profiling via wearable devices.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Consent information -Geo-location data -Environmental (temp, humidity, airflow rate) -Sample acquisition metadata -Analysis of airborne particles, toxins -Metabolomics analysis data (high-res mass spectrometry coupled with liquid chromatography) -Sequence analysis (Illumina NovaSeq platform) 	<p>Participants carry the device with them. Samples collected twice per month. and stored at -20 degrees (two samples per month per participant). Samples delivered to the lab twice monthly and stored at -80 degrees.</p>	<p>Data from 100 devices. -Baseline data (blood, sweat, saliva sample from each participant: 10- 50 GB -Sequence and metabolomics analysis data: TB range</p>

3 Key topics

In order to upload data to the HEAP informatics platform, HEAP researchers need to understand how to manage their datasets with regards to ELSI issues, FAIR data principles and the technical aspects of the Hopsworks-based informatics platform.

In the first three years of the HEAP project and alongside the ongoing development of the informatics platform, the Training and Education element for Knowledge and Information Sharing Phase 1 for the data providers of HEAP has focuses on the following areas:

Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.

Work, led by the WP 2 team, is continuing to fully define the ELSI issues relating to management of personal data and scientific research, and to develop a corresponding ethical and governance framework for HEAP.

This work is ongoing via the following methods:

- The EHEN Working Group on Ethics and Law, with meetings held every three months, with key topics summarised on the [Working Group](#) page of the EHEN website.
- HEAP WP2 Deliverables (D2.1 D2.2)
- Ongoing practical discussions with the HEAP data providers about ethical and legal issues with regards to pilot projects at the BYOD workshops.

The key topics in this area can be summarised as follows:

- General ethical and legal issues regarding exposome research, such as the right to health and research as contributing to a just society.
- Patient consent with regards to cohort studies (broad consent, specific consent, granular consent, consent to governance).
- GDPR legislation, in particular:
 - Roles relating to GDPR, data controller, data processor, joint controllership etc
 - Personal/sensitive data (de-identification, data minimisation measures, encryption).
 - Local approvals and per-project data protection measures.
- The European legal and regulatory landscape with regards to use and exchange of data for medical research (role of European Data Protection Board, European Health Data Space, upcoming EU legal project on AI)
- International transfers of data and materials, Material and Data Transfer Agreements (MDTA) (between EU and non-EU countries)
- Data governance procedures, Data Access Committees.

Data harmonisation and curation

This topic area is led by the WP 7 team and supported by the HEAP representative of the EHEN Metadata working group to support wider sharing within the EHEN network and sustainability beyond the project.

The key topics in this area can be summarised as follows:

- Metadata harmonisation
- Development and deployment of pipelines
- Working collaboratively on datasets, such as developing Machine Learning pipelines for cohort data
- Good practice in data management, such as using FAIR data principles.

HEAP Data Management and analysis services

Technical training in the use of the Hopsworks informatics platform and CSC Infrastructure takes place on an iterative basis between WP6 and WP10 teams and the HEAP data providers from WPs 3,4,5, 8 and 9. As new features become available, these are tested by the data providers who validate the tests and gain new skills in the process.

The key topics in this area can be summarised as follows:

- Definition and use of common metadata (for querying datasets in Hopsworks).
- Definition of analysis tools and pipelines (source code, resources, dependencies, and repositories).
- Installation of tools and implementation of pipelines within Hopsworks and CSC.

4 Learning and informational resources

Scientific papers produced by the HEAP consortia partners are disseminated via the [Resources page](#) of the HEAP website, while the HEAP public deliverables in written format are published on the [HEAP Zenodo community](#).

Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.

During Phase 1 (2020-2022) of the HEAP project, the Ethics and Regulations WP team produced analysis and discussion of the key topics (highlighted in section 3) via publications and reports. In addition to the on-line locations mentioned in the previous paragraph, these materials are summarised on the [Ethics and Law](#) page of the HEAP website, and the [Ethics and Law Working Group](#) page of the European Human Exposome Network website.

The main peer-reviewed publications and reports published on data privacy regulations, and ethical and legal issues during Phase 1, and of direct relevance to the HEAP data providers, are:

- [Joint controllers in large research consortia: a funnel model to distinguish controllers in the sense of the GDPR from other partners in the consortium.](#) *Open Research Europe, June 2022.* This paper proposes a potential model to address the uncertainty about formal controllership under the GDPR that can stifle collaboration in consortia due to concerns over (shared) responsibility and liability.
- [Deliverable 2.1. Report on databases mapped - Human Exposome Assessment Platform \(HEAP\).](#) A common instrument for assessing and addressing data protection requirements involves conducting a data protection impact assessment (DPIA). The purpose of this partial DPIA is to assess where in HEAP which possible threats should be considered, and to provide a roadmap for how to address these further over the coming period. It will be developed iteratively as the project develops.
- [Deliverable 2.2. Report on consumer receipts data and sample-derived data in exposome research.](#) This report covers exposome research in the context of the right to health, discusses how the results of exposome research can contribute to a just society, and outlines the methods by which exposome research adhere to applicable legal and ethical standards. It also includes concrete recommendations on the methods of exposome research and how these should foster trust and enhance participant engagement, focusing on the Danish consumer cohort as a use case.

Planned for Phase 2 (2023-2024):

- A research paper on the theme of patient-facing governance of cohorts, based on answers to a survey on patient consent to participate in research projects by managers of HEAP and EHEN data cohorts.
- A scientific publication on how the results of exposome research can contribute to a just society
- A scientific publication on methods of exposome research that foster trust and enhance participant engagement, via a use case on the Danish consumer cohort study.
- A series of summaries and use cases, including a blog article for the EHEN website, reflecting the key topics as outlined in section 2 above.

Data harmonisation and curation

Publications and reports

During Phase 1 (2020-2022) of the HEAP project, the Data Interoperability and Sharing WP team produced analysis and discussions of the key topics (highlighted in section 3) via publications and reports.

The main peer-reviewed publications and reports published on data harmonisation and curation during Phase 1, and of direct relevance to the HEAP data providers, are:

- [The 10 Commandments of Ethical Medical AI](#). Published in the journal Computer in July 2021 by the WP 7 team from the Medical University of Graz and the WP 2 team from MLCF Foundation. This paper sets out practical guidelines for those applying artificial intelligence to provide a concise checklist to a wide group of stakeholders.
- The [HEAP Data Management Plan \(Deliverable 7.1\)](#), setting out a governance framework and strategy to cover the full data management lifecycle for all of the HEAP data cohorts and projects.
- Report on the [FAIR Toolbox and Bring Your Own Data Workshops \(Deliverable 7.2\)](#), describing the FAIR toolbox, and the FAIR data management training provided during the BYOD Workshops, as well as the technical solutions of the HEAP Information Commons (IC) and Hopsworks tested using sample data from the HEAP data providers.

Learning materials

At the BYOD#2 workshop and in the months following the workshop, the WP11 and WP7 teams worked closely together to produce FAIR data video tutorials (the “Swamped?” series) – five short animated videos summarising the key principles of FAIR data.

The aim of the “Swamped?” videos is to provide an engaging way to support both HEAP researchers and future users of the HEAP platform to ensure their data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) before upload to the HEAP informatics platform.

The series is suitable for a wide audience as it takes a generic approach to FAIR best practice, using HEAP as a practical example.

The process of developing the video series is an example of the WP11 approach to Education and Dissemination through co-creation of resources and is described in detail below.

Development process of the “Swamped?” video series

Outline concept development: Ahead of the HEAP BYOD#2 workshop in October 2021, the WP11 team developed the concept of the video series, which was to realise the twin objective of promoting the HEAP informatics platform as a scientific resource, and creating an engaging introduction to FAIR data good practices for scientific researchers, and provide signposting for further tools and resources, in particular the [FAIR data Self-assessment service](#) developed by HEAP partner Medical University of Graz.

Source material gathering: At the HEAP BYOD#2 workshop (which was held on-line due to on-going COVID restrictions) participants were invited to a “Scripting” work stream” where the source material for the video series was gathered. These were billed as “Data “Storytelling” sessions, and HEAP researchers were asked to present some “real-life” data management challenges that they faced in their everyday work. The sessions were recorded with prior permission from the participants.

Laboratory activities and data – a multi-disciplinary challenge

Figure 1: An extract from a "Data storytelling" presentation from the "Scripting" workflow

Detailed/artistic concept development: The concept artwork and scripts were prepared using the presentations from the BYOD#2 workshop. This work was coordinated by the WP11 team, supported by a science communication agency and with technical input from a panel of "researcher" representatives from the HEAP consortia partners.

Having viewed the "data storytelling" material, the concept of a data lake was highlighted by the creative team. The WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing team (the end client) favoured an approach highlighting good vs poor practice in data management, in particular highlighting the penalties associated with poor practice.

To avoid the pitfall of "blaming" for bad practice, the decision was taken to use animated characters to allow any perception of blame to be "depersonalised", and to enable the characters to be placed in amusing (and relatable) situations to create engagement and emotional connection with the target audience.

To ensure the technical content of the videos was strong and credible, the team decided to combine the animations with real interviews with HEAP researchers. This also enabled the HEAP platform to be promoted as part of the "solution".

This resulted in the final concept of two animated characters, one embodying "bad" working practice, another representing "good" working practice, with support from interviews with HEAP researchers. The data lake concept was extended to encompass a data "swamp" that could be contrasted with a more ordered "laboratory" environment.

FAIR FROG

DATA GATOR

Figure 2: Concept art for the "Swamped?" video series

Figure 3.: Finalised concept with characters/environment

Having developed the concept, the team decided that the best way to deliver the key messages would be via five short videos (an Introductory video plus one video focusing on each of the FAIR principles in turn).

Script development: This was the longest part of the project as it involved considerable input from and debate between the team members in order to decide what the key messages should be and how to present them via appropriate “make believe” and then “real” examples. See Annex 3 for a sample script.

Using the FAIR self-assessment service questionnaire for guidance, the team developed a shortlist of key messages for each video. These key messages were inserted at the top of each script to allow easy sense checking during script development. An example as follows, from the “Accessible script”:

Key messages:

Making data FAIR (ACCESSIBLE) means that you enable others to:

- Easily **get access to** data (once it has been found/located (aka FINDABLE)).
- **Key concepts (for the “Accessible” checklist):**
 - o Accurate and pertinent metadata enabling users to access the data.
 - o Metadata records, that remain available after data is no longer available
 - o Data accessible via standardised protocols and free access protocols, plus protocols supporting authentication and authorization
 - o Manual and automatic access to data (data should be a digital object)
- **Positive message about HEAP** through real research data examples.
- **The FAIR data self assessment service** has been designed by the same team who developed the HEAP platform to help researchers get the most out of their data and contribute to open science principles

Detailed scripting and selection of “real life” examples involved bringing together an “imagined” scenario with FAIR frog and Data Gator, with a “real” example presented in the scripting stream, to illustrate the key messages

from each video, alongside animated situations and scenes that would work in a five-minute video.

This step required a strong grasp of each FAIR concept and many trials and iterations before scripts were finalised and approved for each video.

Storyboarding: Following scripting, a storyboard was produced for each video as shown in the example below:

Figure 4: Storyboard extract from the "Swamped?" series of videos (FAIR data)

Interviews:

Scripted interviews based on the selected "real life" examples were held with selected researchers at the HEAP annual meeting in Graz.

Animation and production:

The animation and production stage involved several iterations to adjust for length and coherence. The original concepts were developed with "Escape from the swamp" and a Data Management survival guide.

Launch and promotion:

The "Swamped?" video series was launched simultaneously on the Heap YouTube channel, HEAP website, EHEN website and HEAP Twitter account.

Following an introductory announcement, the release of the videos was staggered over five weeks to allow a sustained "reminder" campaign to build interest and anticipation of the next video release.

Once the videos were all released, local campaigns from HEAP partner institutions were launched to promote the full series to a wider audience.

The five “Swamped?” videos were released in October/November 2022 on the [HEAP YouTube channel](#). Full details of the launch campaign are available in Annex 4.

HEAP Data Management and analysis services

Publications and reports

During Phase 1 (2020-2022) of the HEAP project, the Informatics Platform and Knowledge Engine (WP6) and Secure Infrastructure for Big Data (WP10) Work Package teams have produced the following reports.

- [Deliverable 6.1. The HEAP Informatics Platform and Knowledge Engine](#). This document summarises the capabilities of the Knowledge Engine within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP), and describes the data management, data warehousing, data sharing and integration with the Information Commons. It also describes the data analysis, feature store, machine learning and pipeline orchestration capabilities.
- [Deliverable 10.1. The HEAP Reference Architecture](#). This document describes the technical architecture, data and metadata flow and means for accessing data in the platform.

The WP 3 team published a scientific paper about a pipeline deployed in HEAP, HPV meta. This pipeline will be tested by other HEAP pilot projects in Phase 2 of the project.

Learning materials

Platform as a Service (Hopsworks, WP6)

The WP11 and WP6 team produced a [“Key features” video](#) about Hopsworks for the HEAP YouTube channel in January 2022.

The WP 6 team maintains [a suite of documentation](#) on the Hopsworks website covering detailed features and tutorials on Hopsworks.

The learning materials planned for Phase 2 of the project include several use case videos, looking specifically at pipeline and synthetic data. The material for this was gathered at the BYOD#3.

HEAP secure infrastructure (CSC, WP10)

The table below summarises the training content currently available for the data providers of HEAP with regards to the secure infrastructure hosted at CSC.

Content title	Description	Target audience/level of prior knowledge required	Format e.g. (documentation, video tutorial, workshop)	Current location
SD-Connect	Detailed information about SD service used for data upload	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	documentation , video	https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd connect/
SD-Desktop	Detailed information about SD service used for processing data in a secure environment	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	documentation , video	https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd desktop/
SD Services	YouTube Playlist of videos found in docs.csc.fi	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wbSf9wR305A&list=PLD5XteVzF3yGtuatGnWmvh39j12lefyp9

The WP10 team provided technical support for the HEAP data providers via regular channels provided by CSC via servicedesk@csc.fi Request Ticketing system, and this consists of support regarding tools, registering accounts at CSC or obtaining resources such as GPUs e.g. for BYOD#3.

Most of the training material and documentation is available via official CSC documentation at docs.csc.fi - including how to request new resources, accounts or how to use the CSC sensitive data services.

There is also a dedicated page for HEAP at CSC: <https://www.csc.fi/-/heap>

Communication

Communication channels for data providers within the HEAP consortia

The table below shows the main communication channels used by data providers within the HEAP Consortia, and their strategic purpose for promoting project goals.

Channel	Purpose
GitHub https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME	Source code repository, used to collaborate and communicate for bio-informaticians, ICT and medical researchers during development of the platform
Slack and Gdrive	Workspace for project members with chat (slack) and common storage functions (gdrive)
HEAP website	The resources page provides easy access to learning resources and key publications

Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/heap-exposome/?page=1&size=20	Repository for technical reports and communications material for the HEAP project
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Communication channels for a general audience

The [HEAP website](#), [e-newsletter](#), [twitter account](#) and [YouTube channel](#), as well as the HEAP page on the [European Human Exposome Network \(EHEN\) website](#), complement the Education and Training element of WP11 by promoting the project’s aims and outcomes to a general audience.

Channels

The table below shows the main external communication channels in detail, and their strategic purpose for promoting project goals.

Channel	Strategic approach	Strategic purpose
HEAP website https://heap-exposome.eu/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provide key, publicly available project information -Provide access to learning resources via a learning platform linked to IARC learning -Later in the project, differentiate parts of the website by stakeholder group (public, policy maker, researcher etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To serve as the main public face of the HEAP project, open to all audiences and delivering all the key messages of the project. -Able to evolve with the project, as new content becomes available and stakeholder groups evolve.
HEAP newsletter https://heap-exposome.eu/newsletter/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Quarterly issue by email to a subscriber base -Focus is on people associated with the project and their work -Format includes one interview per issue, and a summary of exposome events and website news. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Building engagement with the project through a “human interest” aspect -Subscribing to newsletter will build membership of the HEAP site ahead of the Learning Platform being populated
HEAP Twitter account https://twitter.com/heap_exposome As of Dec 2022: 1172 followers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular posts and retweets, planned in a content calendar, to provide ongoing updates on the project - The HEAP twitter account also appears in a feed on the home page of the HEAP website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Network and engagement building with all key audiences -Regular promotion of key messages and events on an ongoing basis - Involving project stakeholders with promoting HEAP
HEAP YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCvTOWwydTW4WcFO6b4kEcVg	Hosting of tutorial videos on legal/ethical, FAIR data and technical aspects of HEAP, and informational videos about the progress of the project	To support the building of an engaged exposome community
European Human Exposome Network website https://www.humanexposome.eu/	To serve as a common focus and source of information and news for all the projects in the network.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To aggregate common information on the exposome -To reduce duplication of content across EHEN project websites -To amplify the common messages of all EHEN projects

Digital campaign approach

The WP11 team manages all project communication channels, and structures and schedules new content to generate interest in the project from a wide audience. An example of this is the digital campaign around the HEAP symposium, which targeted a general scientific audience, in June 2022 (full details in Annex 6).

- Leading up to the event, a [Symposium webpage](#) was created on the HEAP website, and the event was promoted as an EU Green Week event.
- The HEAP Symposium was streamed live on the HEAP website and YouTube channel
- Following the HEAP Symposium, the talks were packaged as a series of 10-minute videos, and released progressively via webposts, which were themselves promoted in a tweet. The posts were staggered over a month-long period (Sept/Oct 2022)
- The talks remain easily accessible as a viewing package via a [HEAP Symposium playlist](#) on the HEAP YouTube account.

Analytics

Heap website:

The graph below shows a comparison of page views between 2021 and 2022, showing a 133% increase in page visits over the past 12 months.

Primary Dimension: Page Page Title Other

Page	Page Views	Unique Page Views	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit	Page Va
	133.72% ↑ 7,021 vs 3,004	111.71% ↑ 5,386 vs 2,544	15.91% ↑ 00:01:42 vs 00:01:28	122.20% ↑ 3,853 vs 1,734	22.35% ↓ 54.99% vs 70.83%	4.93% ↓ 54.88% vs 57.72%	0.0

HEAP twitter account:

Analytics between Sept-Dec 2022.

Tweet activity

Sep 14 – Dec 13, 2022

Export data

Your Tweets earned **10.8K impressions** over this **91 day** period

A snapshot of monthly activity on the HEAP twitter account in November 2022:

Nov 2022 · 30 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 665 impressions

Kicking off the HEAP **#BYOD** workshop in Stockholm with a demonstration of a **#metagenomics** pipeline in **@hopsworks**, with guests from the **#ehen** network projects and **@IARCWHO**
More **#exposome** datasets to follow!
pic.twitter.com/fyd7y9qIES

8 8

Top mention earned 69 engagements

Dr Chiara Herzog
@chiara_herzog · Nov 24

Had a fantastic few (very snowy) days in Sweden, visiting collaborators at **@karolinskaInst** and participating at the bring your own data workshop with **@heap_exposome** (in a castle) 🏰
pic.twitter.com/ZCVWxMNqMt

NOV 2022 SUMMARY

Tweets	8	Tweet impressions	3,513
Profile visits	1,088	Mentions	12
New followers	20		

5 Learning and informational events

In the first 36 months of the project, the WP7 and WP11 teams have held three **Bring Your Own Data workshops (BYOD)**, designed to collectively test and gather feedback on the HEAP platform as it is developed.

Bring Your Own Data Workshops

BYOD workshops are an essential element of the HEAP project. Typically lasting between two and four days, the BYOD brings together project members from different disciplines, enabling them to work in a “hands on” environment.

BYOD workshops are inspired by the “Bring Your Own Device” movement and involve:

- Attendees bringing “real data” to troubleshoot as a collective

- “Hackathon” working, with hands-on activities such as coding, mock-ups, and API tests
- A “Connectathon” approach, to check the interoperability of data and interfaces
- A “Jamboree” format – sessions have no fixed agenda or formal presentations

An example of the collaborative work undertaken at BYOD workshop is the BYOD#3 held in November 2022, with the aim of implementing analysis pipelines, ML models and other research-supporting tools to analyse data from the HEAP cohorts.

To prepare for the workshop, attendees from each pilot project uploaded data and analysis pipelines to the Hopsworks informatics platform.

The aims for the first three days of BYOD#3 were to:

- Design and implement common metadata for querying the datasets in Hopsworks.
- Define the analysis tools installed in the platform: source code, resources, dependencies, repositories, and documentation
- Finally, to install the selected tools and implement the chosen pipelines

Day 4 focused on a presentation of the results, communications planning for the year ahead, and discussions about the sustainability of the HEAP platform.

The agendas of all three HEAP BYOD are attached for further information in Annex 5.

Human Exposome Assessment Roundtables

In 2023 and 2024, WP11 will be launching “**Human Exposome Assessment**” **roundtable sessions**, which are designed for both HEAP and external researchers to discuss and finetune the practical implementation of key aspects of the HEAP platform, such as the wider application of bioinformatic pipelines, and management of datasets (using synthetic data).

These events will bring the material generated and issues raised during the BYOD workshops to an audience of researchers beyond those involved in the HEAP project.

Technical training workshops (Phase 2)

The table below summarises a training workshop planned for the data providers of HEAP (Q1 2023) with regards to the secure infrastructure hosted at CSC, for delivery in Phase 2 of the project.

Content title	Description	Target audience/level of prior knowledge required	Format e.g. (documentation, video tutorial, workshop)	Proposed location
Workshop on CSC SD Services	- Setting up your private workspace with SD services - Accessing data using SD Desktop	HEAP researchers / no prior knowledge required	Workshop	online

6 References

Persona interview approach: <https://www.openlawlab.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/Design-Process-Tool-Persona-Documents-Margaret-Hagan.png>

Joint controllers in large research consortia: a funnel model to distinguish controllers in the sense of the GDPR from other partners in the consortium. *Open Research Europe, June 2022.*
(<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14825.1>)

Report on databases mapped - Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP) (Deliverable 2.1)

Partial DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) to assess where in HEAP which possible threats should be considered, and to provide a roadmap for how to address these further.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7337451>

The 10 Commandments of Ethical Medical AI.

Published in the journal *Computer* in July 2021 by the WP 7 team from the Medical University of Graz and the Work Package 2 team from MLCF Foundation, this paper sets out practical guidelines for those applying artificial intelligence to provide a concise checklist to a wide group of stakeholders.

DOI Bookmark: [10.1109/MC.2021.3074263](https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2021.3074263)

The HEAP Data Management Plan (Deliverable 7.1), setting out a governance framework and strategy to cover the full data management lifecycle for all of the HEAP data cohorts and projects.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4043111>

Report on the **FAIR Toolbox and Bring Your Own Data Workshops (Deliverable 7.2),** describing the FAIR toolbox, and the FAIR data management training provided during the BYOD Workshops, as well as the

technical solutions of the HEAP Information Commons (IC) and Hopsworks tested using sample data from the HEAP data providers.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410291>

The HEAP Informatics Platform and Knowledge Engine. (Deliverable 6.1) This document summarises the capabilities of the Knowledge Engine within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP), and describes the data management, data warehousing, data sharing and integration with the Information Commons. It also describes the data analysis, feature store, machine learning and pipeline orchestration capabilities.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410628>

The HEAP Reference Architecture. (Deliverable 10.1) This document describes the technical architecture, data and metadata flow and means for accessing data in the platform.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4570439>

Annex 1 – Persona interview results for the Data providers stakeholder group (anonymised)

HEAP personas - Epidemiologist #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Defining research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Discovering the potential of the data provided in HEAP to their area of research.</i></p> <p><i>Collaborating with relevant colleagues to access and analyse the data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Will work on real data, therefore they will have ethical / ELSI considerations</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>40-50</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical educational background is: Medical doctor with specialisation in epidemiology</i></p> <p><i>Can define research questions</i></p> <p><i>Has a vision of how the data can be used</i></p> <p><i>Can apply for and receive grant funding.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>Access to data for new projects</i></p> <p><i>To work with existing data sets to get new insights and to achieve their research objectives</i></p> <p><i>Access to the expertise of a data analyst and others to help them achieve their research goals</i></p> <p><i>May not need to directly interact with the platform, (unless with data science background).</i></p>

HEAP personas - Epidemiologist #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Formulating and answering research questions</i></p> <p><i>Accessing data to answer these research questions</i></p> <p><i>Interested in data analysis, secure management and Dissemination in connection with research projects</i></p> <p><i>Particular interests can include maternity cohort data, wearable sensors and HPV vaccination cohorts, and collaborating with other research teams working with this data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>-Ethical and governance requirements associated with data cohorts.</i></p> <p><i>- Ownership of data, e.g. by national governments and national laws governing their use.</i></p> <p><i>-Process of obtaining permits for secondary use of health and social data, e.g. through Findata https://www.findata.fi/ - the Finnish Health and Social Data Permit Authority.</i></p> <p><i>-Setting up the IT system to allow users to access their data, but not on their own premises.</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment</p> <p>category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Medical geneticist,</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>40-50</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical specialisms include metagenomics and epidemiology.</i></p> <p><i>Has access to cohort data and the ability to define research questions</i></p> <p><i>Has access to research funding.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>A connection to Machine Learning technologies</i></p> <p><i>A better understanding of how to use the HEAP platform for Deep Learning analysis.</i></p> <p><i>To understand how consumer data, and clinical medical information can be analysed together to gain new insights</i></p> <p><i>Continuing input and support from colleagues in a collaborative working spirit</i></p>

HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Typical interests include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Formulating and answering research questions. -Coordinating bioinformatics pipelines. -Metagenomics and Next Generation Sequencing (NGS). -Providing interoperable cohort data to researchers in the spirit of open science. -Accessibility of data analytics pipelines for scientists who are not IT specialists -Engagement of civil society - making the case for funding and encouraging the public to consent to their data being used. 	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Would need to follow laws and regulations pertaining to HEAP data (actual rules determined by ethicists/lawyers/project management).</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Profession: Molecular biologist, Research coordinator</p> <p>Age range: <i>40 -50</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical professional profile could include expertise in molecular biology and bioinformatics, as well as experience in handling related data in a research context.</i></p> <p><i>Has access to HEAP data through the HEAP data administrator.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>A very simple and user-friendly interface through which to access HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>The ideal “starting pack” for HEAP - short videos about the platform.</i></p> <p><i>Explaining the concept of exposome in practice (using the partners projects) → also useful to the general public and demonstrating the social value of the research.</i></p> <p><i>Learning more about the other work packages/ projects and teams in HEAP and the EHEN, their working methods and challenges.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Biologist/medical researcher #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Using data to answer research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Prevention of disease incidence and progression.</i></p> <p><i>How to use raw consumer data in research, and the potential and limitations of this data.</i></p> <p><i>Combining consumer data with other data sources such as metagenomic and registry data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Works with real data, which has ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) considerations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-How to protect individuals from being identified/traced through personal data</i> <i>-How to secure consent from users to access their data</i> <i>-GDPR</i> <i>-National laws on consent and on use of consumer and shopping data</i>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Medical doctor. Public health specialist, epidemiologist. Project manager.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>30-40</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Has and can provide access to consumer data.</i></p> <p><i>Can identify new opportunities for the design and application of consumer data to research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Can provide training and expertise in applying consumer data to existing data cohorts.</i></p> <p><i>Conceptualising new uses for consumer data in health care - such as apps where consumer profile data and medical data are entered, and the app users receives tailored health advice.</i></p> <p><i>May also have IT skills, such as R programming, and additional skillsets such as Data impact assessor.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To know how to use the HEAP platform to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-Implement new approaches to data analysis, including new analytical frameworks</i> <p><i>Training needs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-Programming, machine learning models (basic knowledge)</i> <i>-Using “Plug and play” solutions, ready-made analysis pipelines.</i> <p><i>Collaborating with others who have similar data/challenges and interests.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #3

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>The link between external exposures and health outcomes, in particular relating to precision health (including preventative actions) and precision medicine.</i></p> <p><i>Typical interests could include - how external exposures may affect the health of pregnant women and their infants, in the context of a particular data cohort.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Works with real data, which has ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) considerations.</i></p> <p><i>Works with anonymised/coded data, does not see any participants names, and is not involved in recruitment to cohorts.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Postdoctoral scientist.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>30-40</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical specialisms include Pharmacology/toxicology.</i></p> <p><i>Depending on role and research project, can provide access to data - e.g. from wearable sensors.</i></p> <p><i>Depending on role and research project, can identify new opportunities for the design and application of data, e.g. from wearable sensors and devices, in a research context.</i></p> <p><i>Further expertise could include: Personal exposure monitoring schemes, the data that they generate and the interpretations that can result. Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technologies and mass spectrometry to profile personal exposures.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand the legal and regulatory implications and practicalities of conducting an international research project (between EU and non-EU countries) using sensor data and devices.</i></p> <p><i>This includes, where to store/host the sequencing data before, during and after analysis, practicalities of data transfer.</i></p> <p><i>Protocols and guidelines for uploading data in Hopsworks.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #4

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Typical research interests could include: national registry data, cancer registry data. As a specific example - seasonal levels of Vitamin D and the impact of supplement policies introduced in Finland in 2003 and 2010.</i></p> <p><i>Would like to increase awareness of specific data cohorts, e.g. the Finnish Maternity cohort data and sample-related data.</i></p> <p><i>Interested in discovering how data from several cohort studies could be combined for enhanced analysis.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>National data contexts - for example, Findata offers a remote access environment (supported by CSC) for secure data processing. From May 2021 all data processing that utilizes national health registers or combines health and social data from different data controllers will be centralised through Findata.</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical Researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Research coordinator.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>40-50</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Can advise how to request samples and data from cohorts they are working with.</i></p> <p><i>Can advise how to request permission to obtain data from national registries, and be the point of contact for managing requests.</i></p> <p><i>A typical academic background is: university degree in Biochemistry, PhD in Immunology, studying for a Masters degree in Statistics.</i></p> <p><i>A typical area of expertise is reproductive health.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>Video tutorials on how to use the platform. To understand how HEAP could be useful for particular research questions. To see examples of real data being processed by HEAP, such as, for example, Vitamin D manuscripts.</i></p> <p><i>Having an informal/formal platform for knowledge exchange within the Consortia and across work packages.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding the publishing rules within the network and within the consortia.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Epigenomics and understanding environmental effects on health. Areas of focus include diet, nutrition etc.</i></p> <p><i>Longitudinal changes in the epigenome and how that impacts health.</i></p> <p><i>Interested in how data will be stored, and in the informed consent process.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>May have prior knowledge of ethics, for example from writing ethics applications for biobanks, researching information from ethics committees, researching standards, etc.</i></p> <p><i>Aware of sensitivities of genetic data. If data is centralised, aware that data will need to be anonymised.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Bioinformatician</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Post-doctoral scientist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs</p> <p>Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>20-30</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical academic background is: Molecular medicine with a PhD in Neuroscience.</i></p> <p><i>Typical areas of expertise include genomics and molecular biology.</i></p> <p><i>Has expertise in bioinformatics, which could also include industry experience, such as working in precision diagnostics.</i></p> <p><i>May already be using Machine Learning in the course of their current role.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>More information and training on the Hopworks platform. Video introduction and tutorials.</i></p> <p><i>More in-depth/practical aspects of legal and ethical. GDPR, practical application.</i></p> <p><i>Practical workshops where researchers can work jointly on analysing. (BOYD)</i></p> <p><i>Collaboration with other data cohorts to understand their work and common challenges.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>General interests include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Statistical computations for survival data -Data modelling for cancer screening <p><i>HEAP: Inference vs prediction with regards to research questions. Which research questions will use inference, and which prediction?</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Needs to understand and comply with data protection rules relating to national registry data</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Bioinformatician</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Biostatistician</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data processor</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>50-59</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Has access to health registry data.</i></p> <p><i>Makes an impact on government policy through data modelling work.</i></p> <p><i>Can input to training material/programmes in biostatistics.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To improve programming skills in Python and Java.</i></p> <p><i>Access to statistics for multiple comparisons (for multiple sources of data, in particular rich sequencing data).</i></p> <p><i>As a biostatistician, needs to work in collaboration with Bioinformaticians.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #3

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Defining research questions and using bioinformatics tools to run data analysis.</i></p> <p><i>Using HEAP bioinformatics tools and creating new pipelines to answer research questions with HEAP data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Will work on real data, and this work has Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues (ELSI) considerations.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: Bioinformatician</p> <p>Profession: Bioinformatician</p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: Data processor</p> <p>Age range: 30-40</p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical educational profile is: Biologist before completing further training in bioinformatics</i></p> <p><i>Has access to data and can define research questions</i></p> <p><i>Can provide IT-related training on how to use various bioinformatics tools</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>Simple, efficient user interface to analyse data with simple tools.</i></p> <p><i>Clear guidance and tutorials</i></p>

Annex 2: Results of Learning Needs Assessment

Work package 2 - Ethics and regulations		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
HEAP internal stakeholders. Data providers, data processors (WP3,4,5, 8, 9)	Basic/intermediation knowledge of data protection and privacy issues	Seminar/presentation about general overview of GDPR, key terms, to set out the context. Content would include: Data protection, GDPR. A background, and why compliance is importance. Could be a simple presentation or a recorded seminar. Could be delivered by MLF member from WP2 and a Data protection officer from one of the partners, such as CSC. MLF could do 10 mins, GDPO 10 mins, Q&A could last 10 mins. Could run an event within the consortia to begin with.
HEAP internal stakeholders. New Ph.D. students/new joiners with no experience of data protection issues (Work Package Leads should identify them). Data providers, data processors. (also ICT scientists?)	We should assume a limited knowledge of data protection and associated legislation.	Need basic training to become more effective in their role as data providers and data processors. Survey to assess levels of knowledge, followed by 2-hour session on GDPR. Background slides would be the same as for HEAP internal stakeholders, but with more detail, and a longer Q&A. Software tools would need to be covered as well.

<p>"Sustainability" group, consisting of new end users (from 2024 once HEAP becomes an open resource), including policy makers and general public.</p>	<p>For this group, we assume no prior knowledge of legal and ethical matters to do with data protection</p>	<p>Ethics and Legislation (WP2) training proposal (Developed using source material: Deliverable 2.1: Legal mapping and DPIA) Training course: "An overview of data protection, ethics and governance within HEAP" Target audience: Researchers before using HEAP. No prior knowledge of HEAP required.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The HEAP platform – main components (Entitlements Management System, Submission Engine, Information Commons, Knowledge Engine, Data and Feature Warehouse) - The legal context – GDPR etc - The ethical context - Overview of data governance in HEAP. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Who is affected by data governance? (this should describe the target audience for the training and why are they concerned) o Principles: necessity and proportionality of data processing in HEAP: e.g. de-identification, data minimisation measures 2. The HEAP data lifecycle: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of how data moves through the platform, where the approval points are, controls etc (picking up the main components as previously described). Areas to be covered include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Data protection / anonymisation policies and measures for the metadata catalogue, feature store and possible other functions of the warehouse o Security (including encryption) standards and assurances for all different kinds of data, including REMS 3. Data Governance Framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FAIR data principles - Roles and responsibilities in data governance: Data sources, Data custodians, Data processors - The role of the HEAP Data Access Committee (DAC) - Access and use procedures (role-based access control) - Retention periods and policies - HEAP controller/processor framework agreement - HEAP Data subjects' rights policy - Data protection of software and code deployed by researchers on the HEAP platform 4. Data governance in action: Local approvals and per-project data protection measures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Examples of how to adapt HEAP Data governance rules to particular projects, use cases (i.e. adjusting if other instances of platform components are added at other institutions) 5. Data governance in action: International transfers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data sharing beyond the European Economic Area, challenges and legal solutions - Use case overview – wearable sensors, Finnish use cases 6. Further reading and sources of information and advice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tbc, overview of useful sources
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WP6 - Informatics platform and knowledge engine		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Owner/Controller(s) e.g., PI	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of how the data can be used. (need more specific)	Need to learn to how give different types of access (read-only, read-write, etc) to users to data. Learn how to use CSC services (Authorization/REMS).
Data Stewards/Curators	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of the data that they are curating.	Need to understand how to design metadata templates for artifacts (files, tables, features). Need to understand how to start jobs and analyse (high level) the results. Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access).
Data processors - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics.	Need to learn to use Jupyter notebooks and the Hopsworks platform to manage data and libraries. May need to learn to write workflows (Airflow). Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access).
Data Engineering - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Work with large volumes of data, so need to learn data parallel programming (Spark).	Need to learn how to store and process large volumes of data. Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access). May need to learn data parallel programming (Spark)
Machine Learning - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Use machine learning to build predictive models.	Need to learn how to train models, evaluate models, and deploy/use models. Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access).
System Administrator	Knows Unix/Linux operating system and how to manage servers and software.	Installation and configuration of Hopsworks and CSC resources. Learn how to use CSC services.
WP7 - Data interoperability and data sharing		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data providers	FAIR principles. An awareness of what is in the platform (data	FAIR data management -HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS)

	catalogue), platform governance when requesting access to data	<p>-FAIR principles and metadata standards -Hopsworks and CSC tools -FAIR toolbox Apps</p> <p>Trusted repositories -what is a trusted digital repository (together with CSC) -Introduction to HEAP cohort catalogues -dSpace / Fair Data Points</p> <p>DMP updates -lifestyle cohort (Martin) -metadata catalogues (source: WP7 presentation at HEAP Annual Meeting)</p>
WP8 - Epigenomic analysis		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Providers. (These are current WP8 team members, including epigenomics researchers, bioinformaticians)	Will need practical training on aspects of the HEAP platform, in particular WP2 Ethics and Regulations, WPs 6 and 10 relating to Hopsworks and the secure IT infrastructure.	Knowledge sharing events with other WPs. At some stage, they would be interested in sharing information with WP9 (Metagenomics) to find out what they are doing. Learning material on legal aspects of data protection and security, focusing on the risks and ethics/regulations around putting data sets on open access databases due to the risks of identifying individuals.
Data users/end users. (These are likely to be researchers on the epigenome, bioinformaticians, ageing researchers, environmental researchers, mathematicians, biologists. Later on, policy makers and the general public).	The end product would be bioinformatic algorithms, and the end goal is to make a tool to assess the exposome's impact on individuals. Examples of policy impacts would be - e.g.: for a motorway in a narrow valley, what would be the air and noise pollution's impact on the epigenome. The knowledge gap here would be in how to use the algorithm to assess the impact on the epigenome. (what are we expecting in	Training would be on algorithms (e.g., tutorials. What is the prerequisite knowledge to use the algorithms?), what they are and how to apply them. Will need to be designed in a user-friendly way? e.g., Breast cancer risk algorithm - are publicly available. Could be available to the public. This would be relevant towards the end of the project.

	terms of prerequisite knowledge)	
WP9 - Metagenomics analysis		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Providers. (These are current WP9 team members, including metagenomics researchers, bioinformaticians)	WP9 members have required skills and data to complete the WP8 research but will need practical training on aspects of the HEAP platform, in particular WP2 Ethics and Regulations, WPs 6 and 10 relating to Hopsworks and the secure IT infrastructure.	Knowledge sharing events with other WPs. At some stage, they would be interested in sharing information with WP8 (Epigenomics) to find out what they are doing. Learning material on legal aspects of data protection and security, focusing on the risks and ethics/regulations around putting data sets on open access databases due to the risks of identifying individuals.
Data users/end users. (These are current WP9 members as well researchers on the metagenomics, bioinformaticians, ageing researchers, environmental researchers, mathematicians, biologists).	The end product would be bioinformatics pipelines run on the Hopsworks infrastructure, and the end goal is to make a tool to assess the exposome's impact on individuals. The knowledge gap here would be in how to use the pipelines and how to assess the impact on the genomics.	Training would be on pipelines, what they are and how to apply them. Hopsworks should provide user friendly interface to manage and run pipelines. This would be relevant towards the end of the project.
WP10 - Secure infrastructure for big data		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Owner/Controller(s) (e.g., PI)	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of how the data can be used.	Need to learn to how grant different types of access (read-only, read-write, etc) to users to data. Learn how to use CSC services (Authorization/REMS).
Data Stewards/Curators (Data providers)	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of the data that they are	Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access) and how to upload data and structure it into datasets so that correct permissions are allocated.

	submitting and how to structure it.	
System Administrator (ICT scientist)	Knows Unix/Linux operating system and how to manage servers and software.	Installation and configuration of CSC resources and possibly Hopsworks. Learn how to use CSC services and Hopsworks.
Data processor (ICT scientist)	Can program Python, R and Machine learning and AI. Are able to clean and analyse data.	Need to learn Hopsworks and analyse data.

Annex 3: The “Swamped?” video series (FAIR data). Sample script

Title	FAIR data principles and the exposome - Introduction
Runtime	5 minutes

Item	Visuals	Narrative / VO	Time
1	<p>Fair frog sits on a lily pad in a bayou, dressed in a pristine lab coat. Stands up, clears throat, and starts speaking formally.</p> <p>The nose of the Data Gator approaches ominously and dips under the water.</p> <p>The Data Gator rises out of the water underneath the lily pad, the Fair frog on their head.</p> <p>Fair frog hops off Data’s head and starts again. He adjusts lab coat, pulls out a checklist and starts talking, as if giving a lecture.</p> <p>Data rubbing head, interrupts FAIR</p> <p>FAIR sighs and folds up checklist</p>	<p>FAIR: Hello and welcome to the first in a series of short videos about FAIR Data principles and scientific research.</p> <p>I’m the Fair Frog, and...</p> <p>DATA: Sorry, I didn’t see you there, Fair!</p> <p>(To the camera) ... and I’m the Data Gator! Nice to meet you!</p> <p>FAIR: So... I am the FAIR frog and I’m here to tell you about FAIR data, and how it can help us improve the way we work. Firstly...</p> <p>DATA: FAIR data? Sounds like a bit of a headache to me!</p> <p>FAIR: OK. Come with me Data, I think I’d better show you...</p>	30 secs
2	<p>Fair frog hops from his lily pad into a lab, Data follows him, dripping wet, and pulls on a crumpled lab coat.</p> <p>FAIR frog addresses the viewers</p> <p>Data knocks over several test tubes, picks them up, looks muddled.</p> <p>Data holds the test tube up to his snout and discovers elements inside the test tube and his eyes get bigger.</p>	<p>FAIR: (speaking more naturally) What’s one thing that all researchers have in common? We all need to find, share and reuse data!</p> <p>FAIR frog to the audience: But sometimes, and especially when the Data Gator is around, that’s not as easy as it sounds!</p> <p>Academic research offers more knowledge-sharing opportunities than ever before. There’s so much potential for new discoveries, insights and collaborations.</p> <p>But if we want to see the benefits, we all need to make sure our research data is easy to work with.</p>	40 secs

	<p>Fair frog picks up a printout that was next to the test tubes.</p> <p>Hands the printout to Data Gator who looks at it then looks at the test tubes and scratches his head.</p> <p>Data blushes, embarrassed. He surreptitiously bins the paper and throws a lab coat over the pile of test tubes</p>	<p>FAIR frog to Data Gator: Here are those results you asked for.</p> <p>DATA: Are you sure these are the right results? Or maybe these are the wrong samples? Er...</p> <p>FAIR: If you're not sure, how can anybody else be sure?</p> <p>DATA: Er, and what were you saying earlier? Something about data? I'm listening now...</p>	
3	<p>Fair frog hops over the word FAIR.</p> <p>Each word from the acronym FAIR animates on screen.</p> <p>Data Gator yawns and picks up the word 'Reusable' and walks away from FAIR...</p> <p>Fair frog rolls his eyes</p>	<p>FAIR principles help make sure research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>For you, for me, and for anybody else who might want to work with it one day.</p> <p>When data is FAIR, it can be easily collected, connected, linked and integrated with other datasets – to provide insights for other researchers.</p> <p>FAIR: Where are you taking that word, Data?</p> <p>DATA: I'm reusing it! It could come in handy!</p>	30 secs
4	<p>Fair frog is back in the lab. There's a large video screen in the lab. The HEAP logo is on the screen.</p>	<p>Let's take a look at FAIR data principles in action. Let's take exposome data as an example. It can come from Personal Exposome Monitors, consumer receipts, or patient records. It can also come from biological samples.</p> <p>Imagine if we could use computing power to analyse all these different types of data and share them between research projects!</p> <p>I think it's time to meet Roxana, the Project Manager of the Human Exposome Assessment Platform</p>	25 secs
5	<p>FAIR frog interviews Roxana</p>	<p>FAIR: Hi Roxana! Tell us about your project!</p> <p>Roxana: Introduces the HEAP project, mentions a few cohorts, and the objectives of the project.</p> <p>FAIR: Why are FAIR data principles important for a project like this?</p>	2 mins

	<p>Screen walkthrough of the Self-Assessment Service, checking the boxes, pressing send.</p> <p>Screen shows radar diagrams show up from the report</p>	<p>Roxana: HEAP makes it possible to share data and analysis tools to produce knowledge about the impact of the exposome on human health.</p> <p>This can only be achieved by sharing high-quality data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>FAIR: How can researchers be sure that their data is FAIR?</p> <p>Roxana: We have developed a FAIR data Self-Assessment Service, to help researchers check if their data is FAIR. It's available online as a checklist. Once researchers have completed the checklist, they get a report, highlighting areas that need further work.</p> <p>FAIR: Thank you Roxanna, fascinating!</p>	
6	<p>In the bayou - Data hands out pieces of paper labelled 'RESEARCH' to passing dragon flies.</p> <p>Fair Frog takes the remaining research papers from Gator and puts it inside a folder with a padlock on it.</p> <p>FAIR frog zaps the paper held by the dragon fly with their tongue, puts it inside the folder.</p> <p>Data pulls the word reusable out of his pocket and sticks it onto the folder.</p>	<p>FAIR: So, does following the FAIR principles mean that anyone can access and reuse your data? The answer is no.</p> <p>Data can be private, or only shared under certain restrictions, and still be FAIR.</p> <p>And some open data may not be FAIR, if it doesn't have a clear reuse licence, for example.</p> <p>I think you need reminding about reuse licences Data!</p>	30 secs
7	<p>Fair Frog and Data Gator stand side by side in the bayou.</p> <p>Key text words bubble up in the bayou: Discover, store, manage, reuse</p> <p>Data takes a bite out of a document.</p>	<p>Remember, the FAIR principles are designed to help us understand how to discover, store, manage and reuse your data – for the benefit of everyone.</p> <p>DATA: I'm going to watch the other videos on each of the Fair principles. It'll help when I CRUNCH those numbers! Come with me!</p>	20 secs
8	<p>Optional extra scene if video hosted outside the HEAP learning platform</p> <p>www.heap-exposome.eu</p>	<p>FAIR: Visit the HEAP website for more information about how you can use the Fair principles in your research, and to access the Self-Assessment Service</p>	15 secs

Annex 4: Launch and promotion of the “Swamped?” video series

Digital/Social media campaign:

Item title:	Introducing FAIR frog and Data Gator! 7 th November 2022
Web post:	<p>Meet the newest members of the HEAP project team! FAIR frog and Data Gator are scientific researchers from two very different institutions – Swamp Institute, and FAIR Labs.</p> <p>Join them as they escape from the Swamp and find out from HEAP project manager Roxana how important FAIR data principles are to successful research collaborations.</p> <p>Through their adventures, FAIR Frog and Data Gator show why good data management is essential for open science, and for managing the ever-larger datasets available to researchers.</p> <p>The Swamped? series is an engaging introduction to FAIR data principles in five short videos, and features interviews with the HEAP project team, including scientists from Karolinska Institute, University of Oulu and the University of Innsbruck. They share their stories of data triumphs and disasters, and some FAIR data tips and tricks for FAIR frog’s Data Management Survival Guide.</p> <p>The videos also introduce a FAIR data self-assessment tool for researchers, which was developed by the HEAP project team and is available on-line.</p>
Video description (You Tube)	<p>Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 1 - Escape from the swamp.</p> <p>Introducing FAIR frog and Data Gator, the newest members of the HEAP project team! Join them as they escape from the Swamp and find out from HEAP project manager Roxana how important FAIR data principles are to successful research collaborations.</p> <p>This video is the first episode of the Swamped? series - an engaging introduction to FAIR data principles in five short videos featuring interviews with scientists from Karolinska Institute, University of Oulu and the University of Innsbruck. They share their stories of data triumphs and disasters, and some FAIR data tips and tricks for FAIR frog’s Data Management Survival Guide. The videos also introduce a FAIR data self-assessment tool for researchers, which is available on-line.</p>
Tweet	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1589875367283544066

Item title:	Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 2 14 th Nov 2022
Web post:	Join FAIR frog and Data Gator in this 5-minute video as they reach the end of their first joint research project and submit their paper for publication. But there’s a problem.... Data Gator has escaped from the swamp, but it looks like he forgot to bring his metadata with him....

	<p>As Data Gator and FAIR frog battle against the odds to submit their paper, we hear from HEAP researcher Sara as she shares a few stories from her early research career, and explains how these days, she keeps track of her data through Global Unique Identifiers (that persist over time).</p> <p>“Making data findable” is the second instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p> <p>There’s a happy ending, as FAIR frog shows Data Gator the on-line FAIR data self-assessment tool for researchers, developed by the HEAP project team using the FAIR data concepts, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p>
Video description (You Tube)	<p>Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 2 – Adventures with metadata.</p> <p>Join FAIR frog and Data Gator in this 5-minute video as they reach the end of their first joint research project and submit their paper for publication. But there’s a problem.... Data Gator has escaped from the swamp, but it looks like he forgot to bring his metadata with him....</p> <p>As Data Gator and FAIR frog battle against the odds to submit their paper, we hear from HEAP researcher Sara as she shares a few stories from her early research career, and explains how these days, she keeps track of her data through Global Unique Identifiers (that persist over time).</p> <p>“Making data findable” is the second instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p> <p>There’s a happy ending as FAIR frog shows Data Gator the on-line FAIR data self-assessment tool for researchers, which was developed by the HEAP project team using FAIR data concepts, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p>
Tweet	<p>https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1592072812659101697</p>

Item title:	<p>Search for the missing samples! Episode 3 of Swamped?</p> <p>21st November 2022</p>
Web post:	<p>Data Gator launches a search for his missing sediment samples in the latest instalment of Swamped? But the samples are nowhere to found, Gator’s research into swamp ecosystems is doomed, and it’s all metadata’s fault for being boring and confusing...</p> <p>FAIR frog decides to ask Ville, a HEAP researcher, how he uses metadata to keep track of 2 million samples from the Finnish maternity cohort. Ville also explains how the HEAP platform will work, and how scientists will be able to request access to raw data from other studies to make their research truly collaborative.</p>

	<p>“Making data accessible” is the third instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Video description (You Tube)	<p><u>Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 3 – The missing samples.</u></p> <p>Data Gator launches a search for his missing sediment samples in the latest instalment of Swamped? But the samples are nowhere to found, Gator’s research into swamp ecosystems is doomed, and it’s all metadata’s fault for being boring and confusing...</p> <p>FAIR frog decides to ask Ville, a HEAP researcher, how he uses metadata to keep track of 2 million samples from the Finnish maternity cohort. Ville also explains how the HEAP platform will work, and how scientists will be able to request access to raw data from other studies to make their research truly collaborative.</p> <p>“Making data accessible” is the third instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Tweet	<p><u>https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1594585637625159682</u></p>

Item title:	<p><u>A database dilemma... Episode 4 of Swamped?</u></p> <p>28th November 2022</p>
Web post:	<p>Our heroes embark on a new research project, and Data Gator is on the brink of a ground-breaking discovery! But is it all too good to be true?</p> <p>Enter our HEAP researcher Chiara, who shares tips on managing her scientific data and introduces Gator to standardised case report forms, metadata catalogues and unique researcher identifiers.</p> <p>“Making data interoperable” is the fourth instalment of the “Swamped?” video series on why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Video description (You Tube)	<p><u>Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 4 – A Database dilemma.</u></p> <p>Our heroes embark on a new research project, and Data Gator thinks he might be on the brink of a ground-breaking discovery.... But it all sounds a bit too good to be true... Enter our HEAP researcher Chiara, who shares her tips on managing her research data, including standardised case report forms, metadata catalogues and unique researcher identifiers.</p> <p>“Making data interoperable” is the fourth instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Tweet	<p><u>https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1597144773886095361</u></p>

Item title:	<p><u>Final episode of “Swamped?” The Time Machine...</u></p> <p>1st December 2022</p>
Web post:	<p>Faced with an algorithm that can't be commercialised, and patient data that can't be reused for a new study because the consent forms were badly designed, Data Gator resorts to desperate measures...</p> <p>Meanwhile, FAIR frog completes their Data Management Survival Guide with the help of legal expert Evert-Ben Van Veen and gets some more practical tips from researcher Chiara Herzog.</p> <p>“Making data reusable” is the fifth and final instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Video description (You Tube)	<p><u>Swamped? A data management survival guide for researchers. Episode 5 – The Time Machine.</u></p> <p>Faced with an algorithm that can't be commercialised, and patient data that can't be reused for a new study because the consent forms were badly designed, Data Gator resorts to desperate measures...</p> <p>Meanwhile, FAIR frog completes their Data Management Survival Guide with the help of HEAP legal expert Evert-Ben, and some more practical tips from HEAP researcher Chiara.</p> <p>“Making data reusable” is the fifth and final instalment of the “Swamped?” video series, in which our heroes show you why good data management is essential for collaborative research and to uncover new scientific insights.</p>
Tweet	<p><u>https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1598237251154374657</u></p>

Annex 5: Agendas of the HEAP Bring Your Own Data workshops

HEAP Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) Workshop #1

Agenda

FAIR Toolbox and BYOD workshops will provide the FAIR toolbox based on results from the H2020 project B3Africa for the integration of data from different stakeholders, as biobanking, biomedical research, healthcare and other social organizations. Together with tasks 11.3 we will organise several *Bring Your Own Data (BYOD)* workshops. In a BYOD workshop HEAP data provider will get hands-on training (hackathon) and can improve and evaluate the interoperability and FAIRness of their data sets.

When	16th December to 18th December 2020
Where	online by Zoom Plenary and Stream A https://iarc.zoom.us/j/98495124306 . Passcode: 622146 Stream B https://iarc.zoom.us/j/97227027871 . Passcode: 403334
Format	Training Lectures (2-3) Jamborees (2-3)
Audience	Everyone for the morning lectures. Partners will be specifically invited to participate in the two streams
Organizers	Roxana Merino Martinez Anouk Berger Heimo Müller
Governance	Training sessions open for all Heap members Individual streams per invitation by stream chairs
Materials	computer, online access, headphones, microphone
Links	Google Drive Folder for the BOYD Agenda (this document) Attendance List for parallel streams Minutes

Overall Timetable and Zoom Link

16.12.2020	Plenary
9:00 - 9:30 (CET)	Introduction (JD), goals of the meeting, zoom housekeeping, introduction round (HM)
9:30-11:30 (CET)	The Data Management Plan – How HEAP will become FAIR (HM)

11:30-12:00 (CET)	Jamboree goals by the stream chairs (RM, AB)	
	Jamboree Streams	
	Stream A (RM)	Stream B (AB)
13:00 – 17:00 (CET)	Cohorts metadata topic 1: Metadata for sequencing data (KI, TAUH) topic2: Metadata for consumers (SSI)	Future Training & Services topic 1: Data management in HW (LC, CSC) topic 2: Metadata designer/assigner
17.12.2020	Plenary	
9:00 - 9:30 (CET)	Report on day 1 from the stream chairs	
9:30-12:00 (CET)	HEAP Data Management Services	
	Jamboree Streams	
	Stream A (RM)	Stream B (AB)
13:00 – 17:00 (CET)	Cohorts metadata topic 1: Harmonisation of sequencing data from the data providers. Include analysis metadata (KI (PEM), TAUH, ICM) Topic 2: Consumer cohort data harmonisation. How to integrate it into the HEAP?	Future Training & Services topic 1: Metadata in HW (LC). Implementing sequencing metadata in HW
18.12.2020	Plenary	
9:00 - 10:30 (CET)	Report on day 2 and conclusion from the stream chairs (each 30 min)	
11:00 - 11:30 (CET)	HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS)	
12:30-13:00 (CET)	Wrap up and closing	

Detailed Agenda

Training Sessions

The Data Management Plan – How HEAP will become FAIR		
Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to:	Duration: 2h	Session Chair
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the terms in the DMP plan Identify its own project in the DMP Link the DMP requirements to system architecture and the Information Common (IC) 	Methods to be used	Anouk, Zisis
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quiz 	Trainers:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify which metadata standards to use (the must and the shall) • describe what the Information Common (IC) is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation • Lecture • Q&A 	Heimo, Roxana
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HEAP Data Management Services		
Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • go over the HEAP system architecture • oversee CSC services provided to HEAP • what Hopsworks is about • Integration between CSC services and Hopsworks 	Duration: 2 ½ h Methods to be used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration • Discussion • Lecture • Q&A 	Session Chair Heimo, Anouk Trainers: Stefan Negru /CSC Alex Ormenisan/LC

HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS)		
Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • know the motivation for the SAS • understand the questions in the SAS • identify gaps in the data management @home 	Duration: 30 min-1h Methods to be used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration • Discussion • Lecture • Quiz • Q&A 	Session's Coordinator: Anouk, Zisis Trainers: Anouk, Bettina, Heimo

Jamboree Streams

Stream A Cohorts metadata
Chair: Roxana

1. Metadata for sequencing data (KI, TAUH)
 - . Description of the cohorts
 - a. Design of metadata model: Generic model
2. Metadata for consumers (SSI)
 - . Description of the cohorts
 - a. Design of metadata model: Generic model
2. Standardisation of metadata. Includes analysis of data from KI (PEM), TAUH, ICM, UIBK
3. Consumer cohort data standardisation/harmonisation. How to integrate it into the HEAP. Proposal for data analysis

Cervical Screening Cohort - Data Summary:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Hljvokke2Kc_aUq82qddb5U-cjUgFqmaMtFSINfSm3w/edit

Wearable Data Collection - Data Summary:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EV2uBmlNCxf5seGyoUe90Z2rDK-M7zBYxZhCNYYvFQ/edit#heading=h.deh3sxiy2ux>

Maternity Cohort - Data Summary:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1USK-mBxztSBgVjnfKt6eQxolWOHqtVQMm2fXkIX4S2g/edit>

HPV Vaccination Cohort - Data Summary:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jCGNmNfV-Wi-E6ZLcnj1nEw10snpBwG1BfeLYYT7Z0/edit#heading=h.deh3sxiy2ux>

Consumer Cohort - Data Summary:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KXnPLfQfnnA-YIEEH8M1NlmkFza1V1689FoR8SB-vx8/edit#heading=h.deh3sxiy2ux>

Stream B **Training and Services in 2021**
Chair: Anouk and Zisis

Workshop to discuss and identify

- . which supporting services the HEAP project will need in 2021
- a. what are the training needs from all HEAP stakeholders and related resources/events to be developed/planned?

The term “supporting service” is very wide, it covers “non-IT”, e.g. an ELSI consulting service and heavily “IT” service, e.g. metadata editors and mixed tools as the planned “FAIR self-assessment service”. To identify the right services and dissemination/training needs, we will structure the discussion by different stakeholder groups according to their role on the HEAP platform (personas): data providers (e.g. data managers, biobank staff), data processors (e.g. bioinformaticians), data users (e.g. PI’s, laboratory staff), communicators, etc. Services and training can be very “heavy”, e.g. “Hopsworks for Exposome Experts” but also lightweight, e.g. “How a researcher should use Twitter” or “An introduction to HEAP for newcomers”.

HEAP Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) Workshop #2

Agenda

FAIR Toolbox and BYOD workshops will provide the FAIR toolbox based on results from the H2020 project B3Africa for the integration of data from different stakeholders, such as biobanking, biomedical research, healthcare and other social organizations. Together with tasks 11.3 we will organise several *Bring Your Own Data (BYOD)* workshops. In a BYOD workshop HEAP data provider will get hands-on training (hackathon) and can improve and evaluate the interoperability and FAIRness of their data sets.

When 18th October to 20th October 2021

Where online by Zoom
Plenary: <https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94862295774>
Stream A: <https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367> (passcode: SC_1105)
Stream B <https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885>
Stream C <https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572>

Format Training Lectures (2-3)
Jamborees (2-3)

Audience Everyone in the Plenary session.
Partners will be specifically invited to participate in the three streams

Organizers Roxana Merino Martinez
Heather Coombs, Zisis Kozlakidis, Anouk Berger
Heimo Müller

Governance Training sessions open for all Heap members
Individual streams per invitation by stream chairs

Materials computer, online access, headphones, microphone

Links [Google Drive Folder for the BOYD](#)
Agenda for BYOD #2
[Attendance List](#) for parallel streams
Minutes

Overall Timetable

18.10.2021	Plenary
13:00-13:30	Hello and welcome
13:30-17:00	Training session
	“Story telling” stream - introduction and goals Presentation from NRG, ways of working and video development

	Story telling session demonstration		
19.10.2021	Plenary		
9:00 - 9:30 (CEST)	Introduction (JD), goals of the meeting, Zoom housekeeping, Introduction round (HM)		
9:30-10:00 (CEST)	DMP update (revise, new cohort)		
10:00-10:30	Metadata Catalogue		
10:30-11:00	Coffee break		
11:00-11:30	HW update		
11:30-12:00	CSC update		
12:00-13:00	Lunch		
	Jamboree Streams		
	Stream A (AB)	Stream B (PN)	Stream C (RM)
13:00 – 17:00 (CEST)	Data story telling One-on-One Sessions https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367	BYO-Metadata established cohorts (HPV, Maternity, Cervical Screening) Zoom link: https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885 Template: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mCak1iXnITFGLtZ2cX_o0Y1hiwZFYvKsgPH_WLO1jCY/edit?usp=sharing	BYO-Metadata experimental cohorts (Lifestyle, Consumer, Wearable) Zoom link: https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572 Template: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mCak1iXnITFGLtZ2cX_o0Y1hiwZFYvKsgPH_WLO1jCY/edit?usp=sharing
20.10.2020	Plenary		
9:00 - 09:30 (CEST)	Report on day 2 (3 streams) and conclusion from the stream chairs (each 10 mins) Stream A: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1gNnacG6nA15OXrnZKhk7mwP5Pdmul0Z Stream B: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1kTZP6eF_GhA8q7S85Tmu9aQHvFRQ3LAPPDM0mvTZuig/edit#slide=id.p3		

	Stream C: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jT1hJ0M2MYkxgnR9jHwJLabnJdXNDLWBSpZDKwPn5O0/edit?usp=sharing		
09:30 - 10:30 (CEST)	Hopsworks demonstration - data ingest and feature extraction (Hive); registration to further workshops		
10:30-11:00 (CEST)	Coffee break		
11:00-12:00	CSC SD Desktop demonstration; registration to further workshops		
12:00-13:00	Lunch		
13:00-13:30	SAS training https://heap.bibbox.org/surveys/?s=XC8YLX8W8R		
13:30-15:00	Stream A (AB)	Stream B (PN)	Stream C (RM)
general: wish list for F2F meetings	Data storytelling Conclusion https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367	Established Cohort Conclusion https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885	Experimental Cohort Conclusion https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572
15:00-15:30	Coffee break		
15:30-open end	Wrap up and presentation of stream results		

Detailed Agenda

Training Sessions

HW training IC

Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand how to work with HIVE to ingest data and perform SQL queries. Understand how to work with the feature store Understand how to use custom docker image jobs. 	Duration: 60min Methods to be used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation Demonstration Q&A 	Session Chair Trainers: Jim, Alex
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CSC training

Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> know the CSC Services for Sensitive Data understand their connection to HEAP 	Duration: 60min Methods to be used	Session Chair
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> find documentation related to CSC Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation Demonstration Q&A 	Trainers: Francesca, Stefan
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SAS training

HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS)		
Objective: At the end of the session, audience will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> know the motivation for FAIR data management understand the questions/vocabulary of/used in the SAS 	Duration: 30min Methods to be used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstration Discussion Lecture Quiz Q&A 	Session's Coordinator: HM, BK, AB Trainers: HM

Jamboree Streams

Stream A FAIR storytelling (training, videos, tutorials)

HEAP data providers are invited to attend the "Story telling" stream during the BYOD #2 workshop. This is an interactive, one-to-one or small group session for data providers to share their stories with the HEAP WP11 team about challenges they have faced and overcome in preparing and managing research data. The examples can be historic and do not need to be directly related to work with the HEAP project.

The purpose of these sessions is to gather source information for a HEAP "FAIR toolbox" training video series.

<https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367>

Stream B Established Cohorts (Maternity Cohort, HPV vaccination Cohort, Cervical Screening Cohort)

HEAP data providers of established cohorts will

- present in short what work is currently done
- present which metadata/attributes is/are collected in their respected cohort
- discuss common metadata structure/attributes
- discuss aggregable attributes to be put in the (metadata) catalogue

<https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885>

Stream C Experimental Cohorts (Wearable data collection study Cohort, Consumer Cohort, Lifestyle Cohort)

HEAP data providers of experimental cohorts will

- present in short what work is currently done
- present which metadata/attributes is/are collected in their respected cohort
- discuss common metadata structure/attributes
- aggregatable attributes to be put in the (metadata) catalogue

<https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572>

HEAP Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) Workshop #3

Agenda

Stockholm, November 22-25, 2022

Analysis tools link:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1TfaEGqm5MFfoNrUcs8fbhCQ5l481dnn2NBkyMMSLSnY/edit?usp=sharing>

HEAP BYOD #3 highlights

BYOD is a hands-on event to implement analysis pipelines, ML models and other research-supporting tools to analyse data from the HEAP cohorts.

Each partner providing data is responsible for:

1. Meet in advance Hopsworks/CSC colleagues to prepare the implementation of the selected tools and pipelines and pre-upload your data:
 - . **Software and models - Hopsworks:** alex@logicalclocks.com, dhananjay.mukhedkar@ki.se
 - a. **Datasets - CSC:** stefan.negru@csc.fi
 - . **keep in mind** that CSC is not using the services for sensitive data. Consult Stefan N.
2. If possible, implement and test the tools and pipelines in advance
 - . **IMPORTANT:** fill in advance the table in the [link](#). The work of streams B and C depends on this info
 - 2. Bring your own data to test the implemented analysis tools and pipelines
 - 3. **If you have software development skills**, you will be more productive in stream B.
 - 4. **Keep in mind** that the software that you provide should be usable by others, meaning that you should provide brief documentation, scripts for running with parameters as datasets, etc. Contact Alex O. to download and install asap (streams B, C).

BRING YOUR OWN DATA AND YOUR OWN ANALYSIS TOOLS!

Streams Work

The work is organised through 3 work streams, so participants bring resources and skills to each stream. Participants can change streams according to the progress and needs of the streams. The work will be very practical, e.g. implementing python scripts, testing, downloading software, shaping datasets, etc.

Usually, developers meet for a beer or coffee after dinner and continue the work.

STREAMS

Stream	Led	Objective	Expected outcome	Participant profile	Participants
A	Heimo	HEAP Catalogue	Populate Catalogue	FAIR, Hopsworks, data providers	GRAZ, KI, Tampere, SSI, UIBK

FAIR HEAP		FAIR Toolbox	Plan Catalogue- HW integration		
		Cohort papers	FAIR toolbox available		
		Regulatory Paper	Plan for the paper		
B	Alex/Jim	Customisation of HW	Implemented analysis pipelines	Hopsworks, tools and data providers	Hopsworks, KI, Tampere, SSI, UIBK, ICM, CSC
Implementation of analysis tools		Test dockers from partners	Dockers		
		Help to implement analysis pipelines	Test ML from ICM, metagenomics from KI, Tampere		
		Integration with CSC	Help to design ML model for cohorts		
		ICM ML model			
C	Sara / Roxana	Collection of analysis tools from all partners	Description of tools and pipelines	tools and data providers	KI, Tampere, SSI, UIBK, ICM
Collection of analysis tools		Definition of pipelines	Include instruction of implementation and use		
		Provide Stream B with description	Plan for deployment in HW		

AGENDA

Day 1: 22 Nov 2022

Aim

1. Presentation of the new version of Hopsworks
2. Preparation of metadata for omics data based on TCGA repository
3. Definition of participants lists for the work streams

Time	Title	Led/Presenter	Partner
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch		
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome	Joakim Dillner	All

14:10 - 15:00	BYOD plan and plan the stream's member and work	Heimo Müller Heather Coombs Roxana Merino	All
15:00 - 15:30	coffee break		
15:30 - 16:45	Hopsworks: new version overview, how to (query, install, script, execute jobs)	Alex Ormenisan Dhananjay Mukhedkar	all Open to external participants
16:45 - 17:30	Lifestyle Cohort: Hopsworks internal omics repository TCGA style	Martin W. Alex O. Heimo M.	UIBK Hopsworks MUG
18:00	Dinner		

Day 2: 23 Nov 2022

Aim

1. Define the common metadata for querying the datasets in Hopsworks
2. Define the analysis tools installed in the platform: source code, resources, dependencies, and repositories
3. Installation of selected tools
4. Implementation of chosen pipelines

Time	Title	Led/Presenter	Partner
09:30 - 10:30 Stream A	Ethics and regulations: Data Controllershship and Licence Models for Cohort Descriptions; Regulatory Paper Catalogue / Cohort Paper: Update the Cohort Information with each cohort PI Fair Toolbox, Catalogue: Fair Datapoint integration Data Repositories	Heimo M. Evert-Ben V. Heather C. the above and cohort reps. (one after the other) Catarina cohort reps	MUG MLC IARC all data providers all data providers

09:30 - 10:30 Stream B Stream C	Data and analysis tools providers: What data, which tools, what is required? 1. Cervical cancer, metagenomics: Sara, Ainhoa 2. Vaccination, maternity: Ville 3. Consumers: Frederik 4. Wearables: Allison, Ville 5. Lifestyle: Chiara 6. ML applied to metagenomics: Piotr 7. Statistics: Mark	Roxana 1. Sara A. 2. Ville P. 3. Frederik M. 4. Allison Z. 5. Chiara H. 6. Piotr B. 7. Mark C.	KI TAUH SSI KI UIBK ICM KI
10:30 - 10:45	Coffee break		
10:45 - 12:30	Streams work: Stream A Stream B Stream C	Heimo M. Alex O./Jim D. Roxana M.	All
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch		
14:00 - 15:15	Streams work continued		All
15:15 - 15:30	Coffee break		
15:30 - 17:00	Workshop: FAIR toolbox Presentation of the toolbox	Catarina L. Emi J. Heimo M.	all Open to external participants

Day 3: 24 Nov 2022

Aim

- 0. Design/implement the common metadata for querying the datasets in Hopsworks
- 0. Define the analysis tools installed in the platform: source code, resources, dependencies, repositories, and documentation
- 0. Installation of selected tools
- 0. Implementation of chosen pipelines
- 0. Plan demonstrations of work/use cases for the Human Exposome Assessment Roundtables webinar series 2023

Time	Title	Led/Presenter	Partner
09:00 - 09:30	Summary of day 2	Heimo M. Alex O. Sara A.	all
09:30 - 12:00	Streams work Stream A Stream B Stream C (coffee break)	Heimo M. Alex O. Roxana M.	all
12:00 - 13:00	Planning of “Human Exposome Assessment Roundtable” series with use cases/material developed at BYOD#3	Heather C.	all
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch		
14:00 - 17:00	Streams work Stream A Stream B Stream C	Heimo M. Alex O. Roxana M.	all
18:00	Dinner		

Day 4: 25 Nov 2022

Aim

1. Presentation of results from each stream
2. Sustainability debate

Time	Title	Led/Presenter	Partner
09:30 - 10:00	Stream A Presentation of results, cohort catalogues and marker papers	Heimo M.	all
10:00 - 10:30	Stream B Presentation of progress from the implementation of analysis tools and/or pipelines Alex O. to nominate presenters from Stream B	Alex O.	all
10:30 - 11:00	Stream C Presentation progress per data providers Roxana M. to nominate presenters from data providers	Roxana M	all
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break		
11:30 - 12:45	Sustainability of catalogue, data and analysis tools	Joakim D.	all

12:45 - 13:00	Close	Joakim D.	all
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch		

Annex 6: Example of a Digital campaign for a general audience

HEAP symposium highlights series

Digital/Social media campaign

Item title:	<u>Introducing the HEAP Symposium highlights series</u> 21st September 2022
Webpost:	HEAP "Symposium Highlights" showcases the presentations from the "Frontiers in Human Exposome Research" symposium, hosted by BBMRI.at and the Medical University of Graz in June 2022. The Symposium provides a snapshot of the latest exposome research on epigenomics, microbiomics, metabolomics, and the key legal and ethical issues facing researchers. FAIR data, and a preview of the data analysis solution that the HEAP platform is also featured. The 15-minute presentations are now available as a series of videos. To view them, visit the <u>Symposium highlights</u> page.

Item title:	<u>HEAP symposium – "Biobanking and the exposome"</u> 27th September 2022
Webpost:	As part of HEAP's "Symposium Highlights" series, Kurt Zatloukal, Head of the Diagnostic and Research Center for Molecular BioMedicine, Medical University Graz, and Director of BBMRI.at, Austria, discusses how biobanks could add value to exposome research in a 15-minute presentation. Biobanks have expertise in collecting, preserving and providing access to biosamples, as well as processing health data in an ethically and legally compliant, and quality controlled manner. By combining exposome data with biosamples that are linked with health data, the individual genome can be sequenced and by using multi -omics approaches insight into molecular diseases mechanisms and disease outcomes can be obtained. <u>Link to You Tube video</u>
Tweet:	<u>https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1574749102801559552</u>

Item title:	<u>New frontiers in exposome research - the promise of informatics and precision medicine</u> 29th September 2022
Webpost:	The next frontier of exposome research will focus on genomics, transcriptomic, proteomics, and metabolomics, and seek to identify optimal treatments for individual patients. In the next instalment of the HEAP Symposium highlights series, HEAP project coordinator Professor Joakim Dillner explores the

	<p>potential of informatics to make Precision Medicine a reality, outlines the six exposome research projects that will form the proof of concept for the HEAP informatics platform, and presents the HEAP vision of delivering a reproducible informatics tool for exposome researchers, deployable in computer clusters and computing centres worldwide.</p> <p>Link to You Tube video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1575382980511645699

Item title:	HEAP symposium - Measuring the exposome Monday 3rd October
Webpost:	<p>Benedikt Warth is an Associate Professor at the University of Vienna, where he founded the 'Global Exposomics and Biomonitoring Laboratory'.</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP Symposium highlights series, he presents workflows for omic-scale investigations of toxicants, based on liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (LC-MS), and focuses on early-life chemical exposure through analysis of plasma samples from premature infants.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1576887172942073856

Item title:	HEAP symposium - Infrastructures for exposome research Wednesday 5th October
Webpost:	<p>Jana Klánová is Professor of environmental chemistry at Masaryk University in Brno, Czech Republic, and coordinator of the ESFRI Research Infrastructure for human exposome (EIRENE).</p> <p>In her contribution to the HEAP Symposium highlights series, she presents</p> <p>EIRENE RI (Research Infrastructure for EnvIRonmental Exposure assessment in Europe), an EU research infrastructure dedicated to the human exposome, with a particular focus on chemical exposures. EIRENE is designed to enable large-scale interdisciplinary research, providing harmonised workflows covering all processes around data and sample collection.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1577624523586904065

Item title:	HEAP symposium - the exposome and cancer research Friday 7th October
Webpost:	<p>Dr. Zisis Kozlakidis is the Head of Laboratory Services and Biobanking at the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC/WHO). He has significant expertise in the field of biobanking, and has served as President of ISBER.</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP Symposium highlights series, he traces the history of the exposome concept and its link to cancer research, as well as the significant investment in exposome research in recent years, including the creation of dedicated research calls by national and international funding organizations, and concludes with observations and parallels with network building in the field of biobanking.</p>

	Link to video
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1577683981545381889

Item title:	HEAP symposium – Ethics, law and big data Monday 10th October
Webpost:	<p>How can the results of exposome research further the right to health for all? And how can this be achieved in an ethical way, respecting the rights of those whose data and tissue are being used?</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP symposium highlights series, Evert-Ben Van Veen, a lawyer specialising in health and privacy law, explores the tension between individual control over data and tissue, and big data research.</p> <p>Despite the huge challenges this presents, he argues that a balance can be struck through data governance. In the case of data cohorts, good governance can provide clarity and accountability when data and tissue is used for further research or sub-studies.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1579365680734142464

Item title:	HEAP symposium – Exposome data and the HEAP technical platform Tuesday 11th October
Webpost:	<p>How will the Human Exposome Assessment Platform’s data analysis tools work? And how will they add value to exposome research?</p> <p>This HEAP symposium presentation from the platform’s lead architect, Jim Dowling, outlines how the platform can develop, operate, and manage applications and data at scale, and how these capabilities will add value to the data science tools used by exposome researchers, such as Jupyter notebooks, Python, Spark, Flink, and SQL.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1579788608340627456

Item title:	HEAP symposium – personal exposome profiling Wednesday 12th October
Webpost:	<p>Can we prove that someone has been exposed to certain chemicals that have affected their health?</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP symposium highlights series, Michael Snyder, Director of the Center for Genomics and Personalized Medicine, Stanford University School of Medicine, presents his research into individualized environmental exposures.</p> <p>The research compared thousands of chemical and biological components from wearable sensors with thousands of internal biomolecules from biological samples. The research found a strong presence of pesticides, fungicides, herbicides and fungi in</p>

	<p>the samples, and a link between these and affected biomolecules and pathways in the individual's immune system, kidneys, and liver.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1580203888044494850

Item title:	HEAP symposium – DNA markers, ageing and lifestyle Friday 14th October
Webpost:	<p>How does age, and lifestyle factors such as drugs, hormones, smoking, and nutrition, affect our DNA?</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP symposium highlights series, Martin Widschwendter, Director of the European Translational Oncology Prevention and Screening (EUTOPS) Institute, University of Innsbruck, Austria, presents his research into DNA markers that are changed by both genetic and lifestyle factors. These markers, or DNA methylation signatures called epigenetic 'clocks', can be used to measure the ageing process of cells, and have been found to accurately predict chronological age or how many divisions a cell has undergone.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1580844876299919361

Item title:	HEAP symposium – Personalised preventive medicine using epigenetics Monday 17th October
Webpost:	<p>Can we predict someone's risk of developing cancer by looking at their DNA markers?</p> <p>In her contribution to the HEAP symposium highlights series, Chiara Herzog, Postdoctoral researcher, European Translational Oncology Prevention and Screening (EUTOPS) Institute, University of Innsbruck, presents the HEAP Lifestyle cohort, and her research into risk identification (WID) for breast or ovarian cancers by looking at DNA markers, and how these change over time.</p> <p>Link to video</p>
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1581910883441455104

Item title:	HEAP symposium – How what we buy affects our health Tuesday 18th October
Webpost:	<p>How do our everyday purchases affect our health?</p> <p>In his contribution to the HEAP symposium highlights series, Frederik Trier Møller, leader of HEAP's Consumer Cohort, outlines how Consumer Purchase Data (CPD) from loyalty programs and digital receipts can be used to assess the effect of consumer products on our health.</p> <p>He introduces the GDPR-compliant, secure, encrypted web application developed by HEAP researchers with consent from participants, retrieving consumer data from three of the five</p>

	largest retail chains in Denmark, and explains how this data is being linked to health outcomes. Link to video
Tweet:	https://twitter.com/heap_exposome/status/1582359412311986178